

MULTISCALE ANALYSES OF WOVEN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES: DAMAGE MODELING

C. Fagiano¹, A. Doitrand¹, V. Chiaruttini¹, M. Hirsekorn¹

¹Department of Composite Materials and Structures, Onera The French Aerospace Lab
29 avenue de la division Leclerc 92322 Châtillon cedex, France
Email: christian.fagiano@onera.fr

Keywords: Textile composites, Damage mechanics, Finite element analysis, Multiscale modeling

ABSTRACT

The mechanical behaviour of woven composites is modelled at the mesoscopic scale, taking into account the influence of the dry fabric preforming before resin injection, the relative shift and nesting between fabric layers, and the effect of yarn cracking and micro-decohesions at the yarn surface. The strain distributions observed at the composite surface are strongly influenced by the layer shift. A good agreement with strain distributions observed by Digital Image Correlation is obtained only if the layer shifts are similar to those observed in the real specimen. Mesoscopic damage is modelled by introducing discrete cracks in the Finite Element mesh of the Representative Unit Cell of the composite. The crack locations in the yarns are determined using a stress based failure criterion. The predicted locations are similar to those observed experimentally. The effects of mesoscopic scale damage on the macroscopic mechanical properties are evaluated. The numerical results show similar trends as the experimental data. However, in order to reach a quantitative agreement, the effect of micro-decohesions around the crack tips at the yarn surfaces have to be taken into account.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials manufactured using textile architectures are receiving a growing interest in the field of advanced structural applications. The main reasons are related to the fact that the microstructure of fiber preforms can be tailored to satisfy specific needs in terms of mechanical performance. Complex reinforcement shapes may be directly woven with modern looms [1], which reduces the number of parts needed to assemble a composite structure, hence limiting the use of joints, which are classical weak points, and reducing the manufacturing costs.

In recent years, Onera has developed macroscopic models that successfully predict damage evolution and failure in textile composites [2;3]. Nevertheless, if the constituents or the reinforcement architecture of the composite change, expensive and time consuming experimental tests are necessary to re-identify the parameters of the models. Virtual material testing is a possible strategy for replacing some of the experimental tests during the design phase. For that purpose, predictive models based on a more physical description of damage are necessary. These models have to link the different characteristic scales of the material [4]. The microscopic scale is the scale of the constituents (fiber and matrix). At the mesoscopic scale, the reinforcement architecture is described by interlaced homogeneous fiber yarns embedded in the matrix. The macroscopic scale is the scale of the structure, at which the material is considered to be homogeneous. In order to set up predictive macroscopic damage models taking into account the reinforcement architecture, accurate damage modeling at the mesoscopic scale is required. At the mesoscopic scale, the Representative Unit Cell (RUC) is a part of the textile reinforcement describing the interlacing of warp and weft yarns of the composite.

Most textile composites are manufactured using matrix injection/infusion, or thermoforming. In order to increase the fiber volume fraction in the composite to improve its mechanical performances, the preform is usually compacted before adding the matrix. This has a significant influence on the yarn shape and paths and must therefore be taken into account in the mesoscopic RUC. Indeed, complex yarn shapes can be generated during the manufacturing process, including (i) local variations of both

the section and the fiber volume fraction in the yarns [5;6], (ii) random shifts and nesting between the layers [5;7;8], and/or (iii) complex contact zones between the yarns. The shape and orientation of the yarns and their interaction have an important influence on the local strain/stress distributions of the composite under mechanical loading, as well as on damage initiation and propagation [9-11]. For instance, it has been shown in different studies that the nesting between the layers of a multilayered textile composite has to be taken into account since it can lead to different damage initiation conditions, and different scenarios of damage progression [11-14]. Therefore, at the mesoscopic scale, it is extremely important to generate geometries with yarn shapes as close as possible to reality.

Several automated tools have been proposed throughout the last decade to generate geometrical models of fabric reinforcements, and covering a huge variety of weaving patterns [15-18]. However, the deformation occurring during the preforming step of the fabric is often neglected. In fact, an idealized geometric model of the fabric is commonly adopted, resulting in resin rich areas that are bigger than those observed experimentally. As a consequence, in order to preserve the overall fiber volume fraction in the composite (typically between 50 and 60%), the fiber volume fraction in the yarns must be set to higher values than observed in reality (sometimes 90%, or higher [19]). Yarn shapes closer to those of the real composite can be obtained from Finite Element (FE) modeling of the dry fabric preforming [20-24]. These methods are used in this work to create geometries of a slightly unbalanced four-layer plain weave fabric with different types of nesting between the layers.

In this work, an algorithm developed at ONERA [25], able to mesh multi-layer 2D fabric architectures as well as the injected matrix complement (section 2.1), is used to generate RUC meshes that are conformal at the contact zones (section 2.2). The algorithm avoids the introduction of artificial matrix layers in the contact zones, as done for instance in [4;13;26-28] to simplify the meshing procedure.

There are two ways of modeling damage at the mesoscopic scale. Approaches based on continuum damage mechanics have been often used to simulate the damage mechanisms [4;9;26;27]. The advantage of these methods is that they are based on damage variables able to predict the degraded stiffness. Being usually combined with well-established failure criteria, continuum damage models show, in general, robust damage detection. However, when it comes to damage propagation the calculations can show non-physical behaviours [4]. In this case, the second approach that consists in introducing discrete cracks directly into the mesh seems to be necessary to predict the behavior of a woven composite structure.

The aim of this work is to model the characteristic damage mechanisms encountered at the mesoscopic scale and to evaluate their effects on the macroscopic mechanical behavior of the material. The generation and meshing of a compacted RUC is presented in Section 2. Then, the local strain distributions obtained using mesoscopic FE simulations are compared with those obtained experimentally using stereo digital image correlation (section 3). Finally, the sequence of intra-yarn transverse damage has been characterized thanks to microscopic observations on the tested specimens, and the numerical discrete damage modeling is presented in section 4. This is done using the crack insertion algorithm developed by Chiaruttini et al. [29]. The effects of mesoscopic scale transverse damage on the macroscopic mechanical properties of the composite are evaluated and compared with the experimental data (section 5).

2 GENERATION OF A COMPACTED REPRESENTATIVE UNIT CELL

2.1 Modeling of fabric compaction and nesting

The material studied in this work is a four-layer plain weave fabric of glass fiber and epoxy matrix. The advantage of modeling such architecture is that it has a relatively simple geometry with a small RUC. Nevertheless, due to compaction and nesting, the compacted reinforcement exhibits multiple contacts zones between yarns that are significantly deformed with respect to their initial shape. Modeling the preforming step of the dry reinforcement allows for generating such reinforcement geometries. First, four layers of a plain weave unit cell are generated and stacked on top of each other. The Hivet and Boisse procedure [30] is used and ensures no interpenetrations between yarns. Second, the layers are shifted with respect to one another in the fabric plane. The relative layer shifts are determined from experimental observations. They are then cut at the boundaries of the unit cell box,

such that each layer is limited to the same unit cell. Figure 1a shows the FE mesh of such a lay-up in the case of maximum nesting. The dry fabric is then compacted using a method similar to that of Nguyen et al. [23]. The preforming step was simulated using Abaqus Standard. A simplified mechanical behaviour is used for the yarns [22], which in the case of compaction modeling yields qualitatively good yarn shapes. Figure 1b shows the results of the preforming step of a four layer plain weave RUC with maximum nesting, compacted from an initial thickness of 2.9mm to a final thickness of 1.65mm. The local yarn orientations at each integration point are obtained by projection of its position onto the yarn center line. The yarn volume fraction (total volume occupied by yarns divided by the total volume of the unit cell) is 52.0% in the non-compacted state and 87.3% after compaction. Therefore, in order to obtain a total fiber volume fraction in the composite of 60% (a typical value for compacted fabrics), the fiber volume fraction in the yarns would reach an unphysical value of 115% if a non-compacted geometry as in [11;13;26] is used. Ivanov [19] has encountered the same problem for braided fabrics. Using the compacted unit cell shown in Fig. 1b, the fiber volume fraction in the yarns has to be 68.7% so as to reach 60% of total fiber volume fraction in the composite.

Figure 1: FE simulation of the compaction of four layers of plain weave fabric with maximum nesting. The colours in (b) represent the magnitude of the vertical displacement.

2.2 Generation of consistent Finite Element mesh of the Representative Unit Cell

It is quite easy to generate FE meshes of yarns by using automated meshing tools. However, it poses a challenge to obtain meshes that are conformal where yarns are in contact. A conformal mesh is obtained if the surface nodes of each yarn are at the same locations in the contact zone. During the compaction of the dry fabric, the yarn surfaces may slide on each other, leading to non-conformal meshes, even if the initial non-preformed meshes were generated with conformal contact zones. Therefore, an algorithm has been developed at Onera to generate consistent meshes of yarns of arbitrary shapes that are conformal at the contact zones. Small interpenetrations and voids that are sometimes generated by the contact interactions used in the modeling of the preforming step are eliminated by the algorithm. More details about this algorithm can be found in the work of Grail et al [25]. Figure 2 shows the resulting FE mesh of a compacted lay-up of four layers of plain weave with the layer shifts taken from experimental observations.

3 EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND COMPARISON WITH THE NUMERICAL MODELING

Experimental tests were performed at Onera for different four-layer plain weave fabric composites specimens under uni-axial static tensile load to (i) determine local strain distributions in the plies and (ii) characterize the onset and patterns of progressive damage mechanisms. A plain weave architecture was chosen because it is the smallest pattern commonly used, which simplifies the comparison between experimental analyses and numerical simulations. The reinforcement is made of E-Glass fibers. The epoxy matrix is the Araldite LY564 produced by Huntsman. Different specimens have been tested under different load protocols, e.g., monotonic and incremental loadings. In contrast to unidirectional composites, the yarn interlacing pattern in textile composites causes heterogeneous strain fields with large strain gradients around yarn crimp regions. Classical electrical resistance strain

gauges can thus not provide an adequate spatial resolution. Therefore, the local strains on the composite surface have been measured using Digital Images Correlation (see Figure 3). In addition, both acoustic emission and microscopic analyses have been used in order to understand the local damage behaviour.

Figure 2: Optimized FE mesh of the compacted RUC with the experimentally observed shift between the fabric layers. (a) Total RUC with matrix complement. (b) Mesh of the yarns only.

These multi-instrumented tests are performed in order to predict the damage onset in the composite in terms of stress and location. Moreover, the density and total length of the visible cracks on the composite edge are measured under an optical microscope. For all the tested specimens, the number of visible cracks transverse to the loading direction was measured. In the case of specimens subjected to incremental loadings, the number of cracks/mm², ρ_s , is calculated at each loading step. The damage observed just before failure is shown in Fig 4 (this picture was not taken at the failure location). Transverse yarn cracks are observed with micro-decohesions between the yarns in contact, and matrix plastification and damage around the crack tips.

The procedure presented in Section 2 is used to generate FE meshes of a RUC with different shifts between the fabric layers: (i) no shift (and thus no nesting), (ii) the layer shift allowing for maximum nesting (see Figure 1), and (iii) the layer shifts observed experimentally (Figure 2). Periodic boundary conditions are applied in the direction of the warp and the weft yarns. The top and bottom surfaces are stress free, as in the experiment. The elastic properties of the matrix provided by the manufacturer are $E_m=3.2$ GPa and $\nu_m=0.35$. The properties of the E-glass fiber are $E_f=72.4$ GPa and $\nu_f=0.2$. The homogenized properties of the yarns are calculated by performing a FE calculation at the microscopic scale, as done by Melro et al [26]. The fiber orientation at each integration point is given by projection on the yarn center line. The homogenized elastic properties are calculated from the average stress and strain over the RUC.

The macroscopic elastic properties calculated by FE simulations are in good agreement with the experimental data. The elastic properties obtained (i) numerically with different nesting between the layers and (ii) experimentally are presented in Tab 1. The nesting between the layers has a negligible influence on the macroscopic homogenized properties of the material. The strain fields at the top surface of the RUC obtained for different nested RUC are compared to experimental observations in Fig. 3. The local strain distribution is strongly influenced by the shift between the fabric layers. The differences in the strain pattern are due to the relative position of the layers to one another and the difference of yarn shapes obtained after compaction modeling. The surface strain distributions agree well between numerical and experimental results only if the same relative layer positions as in the studied specimen are used to generate the RUC of the composite.

Figure 3: Longitudinal (ϵ_{11}) and transverse (ϵ_{22}) strain fields obtained experimentally by digital image correlation on the top surface of a composite specimen with four layers of plain weave reinforcement under tensile load in direction of the blue arrows ($\sigma_{11}=90\text{MPa}$). The experimental patterns are compared to FE simulations of four adjacent RUC with different layer shifts: (a) shifts of the specimen, (b) shifts to obtain maximum nesting, and (c) no shifts.

Figure 4: Damage pattern observed by optical microscopy on the specimen edge just before failure (the image was not taken at the failure location).

Method	Nesting	E11 (GPa)	E22 (GPa)	G12 (GPa)	ν_{12}
EF	Zero	21.5	22.7	6.63	0.14
EF	Max	21.3	22.6	6.60	0.14
EF	random	20.9	22.4	6.47	0.13
MT	random	21.2	22.6	6.46	0.12
Tests	/	21.48 ± 0.58	24.18 ± 1.14	6.25 ± 0.35	0.127 ± 0.014

Table 1: Macroscopic elastic properties of the four-layer plain architecture obtained (i) numerically (EF) by taking into account three different types of nesting between the layers, (ii) analytically (MT) [30] and (iii) experimentally with confidence intervals of 95%.

4 INFLUENCE OF DAMAGE ON THE MACROSCOPIC HOMOGENIZED ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF THE COMPOSITE

In this work, mesoscopic damage is modeled by inserting discrete cracks in the FE mesh of the RUC, using the algorithm of Chiaruttini et al [29]. This algorithm allows the simulation of complex cracks growth phenomena, and one of the advantages of this approach is that almost any kind of crack can be introduced in very complex meshes. It is based on the modification of an initial undamaged mesh that is refined in the vicinity of the crack front. First, the crack surface is represented by a surface mesh made of linear triangular elements. Then, the undamaged zone of the volume mesh is adapted such that the crack can be inserted. A volume remeshing operation is finally applied to the complete mesh. The main advantage of introducing discrete damage in the RUC mesh is that the influence of damage on the local stress state can be directly observed. In this work, a failure criterion developed for unidirectional plies is used for the yarn [31], and a failure criterion for quasi-brittle materials is used for the matrix [32]. These two failure criteria have already been used in a previous study in order to determine the damage onset mechanism and location in woven composites [33].

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the damage modeling algorithm: (a) undamaged RUC, (b) prediction of crack locations through a failure criterion, (c) insertion of cracks at the predicted locations and (d) prediction of new cracks resulting from the failure criterion applied to the damaged RUC.

Experimental observations show that at the mesoscopic scale, damage starts by cracking of the yarns that are transversely oriented to the load direction. Debonding at the yarn surface is observed at the crack tips. Several hypotheses are made concerning the geometry of the crack. The first assumption is that the crack, once nucleated, is supposed to propagate instantaneously across the whole yarn. Obert et al. [34] justified this assumption by arguing that the energy density is nearly uniform along a yarn. The second assumption is that the decohesion length is supposed to be constant and symmetric on each side of the crack, and that the crack plane is perpendicular to the macroscopic loading direction. The first step in the crack insertion process consists in determining the location of the first cracks in the undamaged RUC using the failure criterion described above (Figure 5a and b). At these locations, cracks are inserted into the FE mesh (Figure 5c). Then, a calculation with the damaged RUC leads to the determination of the location of new cracks (Figure 5d) that are also inserted into the RUC mesh. This process is repeated until the crack density in the RUC is close to the crack density measured experimentally at failure. A random nesting between the layers is used so that yarn position and shape is as close as possible to experimental observations. Micro-decohesions of different lengths are also generated around the crack tip. Final damaged RUCs of four layers of plain weave fabric with transverse cracks in the weft yarns and yarn/yarn and yarn/matrix decohesion around the crack tips are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Representative Unit Cell of four layers of plain weave fabric with transverse cracks in the weft yarns and yarn/yarn and yarn/matrix decohesion around the crack tips: (a) one crack per weft yarn, (b) two cracks per weft yarn.

The homogenized elastic properties are calculated by FE simulations using the method described in Section 3. The decrease of elastic properties with growing crack density ρ_s is compared to the experimental results in Fig. 7. The results show that the trend of the evolution of Young's modulus and Poisson ratio with the crack density is well predicted by the numerical simulations. The reduction of the properties is slightly underestimated if micro-decohesions are not included. An average decohesion length around the crack tip of 0.1mm gives better results. It has to be noted that in reality the cracks may not cover the whole width of the specimen. However, it is impossible to determine their actual length without a micro-CT analysis. Such results are not available for the time being, but a study is planned to take place in the near future. Therefore, numerical simulations may overestimate the reduction of the elastic properties, since the total crack surface may be overestimated for a given number of cracks. This leads to the conclusion that the correct average micro-decohesion length is probably higher than 0.1mm.

Figure 7: Comparison between experimental and numerical results of the effect of transverse cracks in the weft yarns on Young's modulus (a) and Poisson ratio (b) in warp direction as function of the crack density ρ_s and the micro-decohesion length μ .

5 CONCLUSION

A strategy for the numerical modeling of damage in woven composites at the mesoscopic scale has been presented. The complex geometry of the reinforcement in the RUC is correctly described since the influence of dry fabric preforming before resin injection is taken into account by modeling the fabric compaction. Consistent FE meshes are generated without the need of inserting a matrix layer between yarns. Several unit cells of four layers of plain weave fabric with different shifts between the layers have been studied. Comparison with strain fields observed by DIC on the surface of the specimens shows that the numerical results are in good agreement with the experimental tests, qualitatively and quantitatively, only if random shifts between the fabric layers are included in the model. The macroscopic elastic properties calculated numerically obtained through periodic Finite Element (FE) homogenization were also evaluated, and the results are in good agreement with the experimental data, whatever the layer shift. Hence, the nesting between the layers seems to have a negligible influence on the calculation of the macroscopic elastic properties of the material. Due to a better correlation in terms of surface strain fields, damage has been introduced into the FE model of

the RUC with random shifts between the fabric layers. This was done by inserting transverse yarn cracks, detected by means of a stress based failure criterion, and micro-decohesions at the yarn surfaces around the crack tips. The evolution of the elastic properties obtained from numerical simulations show the same trends as observed by experiments. To obtain a good quantitative agreement in the property reduction due to damage, micro-decohesions around the crack tips have to be included in the model. Despite the simplified crack geometry, the results are encouraging. Future developments will concern a more detailed modeling of the characteristic damage mechanisms and their kinetic based on micro-CT observations and infrared thermography. These non-destructive testing technics are useful to better understand the damage mechanisms inside the material and to validate the modeling hypotheses, in particular the crack length along the yarns and the size of the decohesion zones. The non-linear behavior of both the yarns and the matrix will be also taken into account.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Mouritz, M. Bannister, P. Falzon, K. Leong. "Review of applications for advanced three-dimensional fibre textile composites". *Compos Part A- Appl S*, Vol. 30, pp. 1444-61, 1999.
- [2] L. Marcin. *Modélisation du comportement, de l'endommagement et de la rupture de composites à renforts tissés pour le dimensionnement robuste de structures*. Ph.D. Thesis, Université de Bordeaux 1, 2010.
- [3] C. Rakotoarisoa, F. Laurin, M. Hirsekorn, J.-F. Maire, L. Olivier. Development of a fatigue model for 3d woven polymer matrix composites based on a damage model. In *Proceedings of ECCM15*, Venice, Italy, 2011, paper 101.
- [4] S. V. Lomov, D. S. Ivanov, I. Verpoest, M. Zako, T. Kurashiki, H. Nakai. Meso-FE modeling of textile composites: Road map, data flow and algorithms. *Composites Science and Technology* 67(9):1870-1891, 2007.
- [5] M. Olave, A. Vanaerschot, S.V. Lomov, D. Vandepitte. "Internal geometry variability of two woven composites and related variability of the stiffness". *Polym Compos*, Vol. 33, No. 8, pp. 1335-50, 2012.
- [6] M. Karahan, S. V. Lomov, A. E. Bogdanovich, D. Mungalov, I. Verpoest. "Internal geometry evaluation of non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven carbon fabric composite". *Compos Part A- Appl S*, Vol. 41, No. 9, pp. 1301-11, 2010.
- [7] B. Chen, E. J. Lang, T. W. Chou. "Experimental and theoretical studies of fabric compaction behavior in resin transfer molding". *Mater Sci Eng*. Vol. 317, No.1, pp. 188-96, 2001.
- [8] S. V. Lomov, I. Verpoest, T. Peeters, D. Roose, M. Zako. "Nesting in textile laminates: geometrical modeling of the laminate". *Compos Sci Technol*. Vol. 63, No. 7, pp. 993-1007, 2003.
- [9] S. Daggumati, I. De Baere, W. Van Paeppegem, J. Degrieck, J. Xu, S.V. Lomov, et al. "Local damage in a 5-harness satin weave composite under static tension: Part I Experimental analysis". *Compos Sci Technol*. Vol. 70, No. 13, pp. 1926-33, 2010.
- [10] S. John, I. Herszberg, F. Coman. "Longitudinal and transverse damage taxonomy in woven composite components". *Compos Part B-Eng*. Vol. 32, No. 8, pp. 659-68, 2001.
- [11] B. H. Le Page, F. J. Guild, S. L. Ogin, P.A. Smith. "Finite element simulation of woven fabric composites". *Compos Part A- Appl S*. Vol. 35, No. 7, pp. 861-72, 2004.
- [12] N. V. De Carvalho, S. T. Pinho, P. Robinson. "An experimental study of failure initiation and propagation in 2D woven composites under compression". *Compos Sci Technol*. Vol. 71, No. 10, pp. 1316-25, 2011.
- [13] N. V. De Carvalho, S.T. Pinho, P. Robinson. "Numerical modeling of woven composites: Biaxial loading". *Compos Part A- Appl S*. Vol. 43, No. 8, pp. 1326-37, 2012.
- [14] K. Woo, J. D. Whitcomb. "Effects of fiber tow misalignment on the engineering properties of plain weave textile composites". *Compos*

- [15] I. Verpoest, S. V. Lomov "Virtual textile composites software WiseTex: Integration with micro-mechanical, permeability and structural analysis". *Compos Sci Technol*. Vol. 65, No. 15-16, pp. 2563-74, 2005.
- [16] M. Sherburn. "Geometric and mechanical modeling of textiles". *The University of Nottingham*, 2007.
- [17] G. Couegnat. "Approche multiéchelle du comportement mécanique de matériaux composites à renfort tissé". *Université Bordeaux I*; 2008.
- [18] S. Adanur, T. Liao. "3D modeling of textile composite performs". *Compos Part B-Eng*. Vol. 29, No. 6, pp.787-93, 1998.
- [19] D. S. Ivanov, F. Baudry, B. Van Den Broucke, S. V. Lomov, H. Xie, I. Verpoest. Failure analysis of triaxial braided composite. *Composites Science and Technology* 69(9):1372-1380, 2009.
- [20] P. Badel, E. Vidal-Sallé, E. Maire, P. Boisse. "Simulation and tomography analysis of textile composite reinforcement deformation at the mesoscopic scale". *Compos Sci Technol*. Vol. 68, No. 12, pp. 2433-40, 2008.
- [21] P. Badel, E. Vidal-Sallé, P. Boisse. "Computational determination of in-plane shear mechanical behaviour of textile composite reinforcements". *Comp Mater Sci* Vol. 40, No. 4, pp. 439-48, 2007.
- [22] L. Hua, M. Sherburn, J. Crookston, A. Long, M. Clifford, I. Jones. "Finite element modeling of fabric compression". *Model Simul Sci Eng*. Vol. 16, No. 3, 2008.
- [23] Q. T. Nguyen, E. Vidal-Sallé, P. Boisse, C. H. Park, A. Saouab, J. Bréard, et al. "Mesoscopic scale analyses of textile composite reinforcement compaction". *Compos Part B-Eng*. Vol. 44, pp. 231-41, 2013.
- [24] F. Stig, S. Hallström. "Spatial modeling of 3D-woven textiles". *Compos Struct*. Vol. 94, No. 5, pp. 1495-502, 2012.
- [25] G. Grail, M. Hirsekorn, A. Wendling, G. Hivet, R. Hambli. "Consistent Finite Element mesh generation for meso-scale modeling of textile composites with preformed and compacted reinforcements". *Submitted to Compos Part A- Appl S*, 2013.
- [26] A. R. Melro, P. P. Camanho, F. M. Andrade Pires, S. T. Pinho. "Numerical simulation of the non-linear deformation of 5-harness satin weaves". *Comp Mater Sci* Vol. 61, No. 0, pp. 116-26, 2012.
- [27] S. V. Lomov, P. Boisse, E. Deluycker, F. Morestin, K. Vanclooster, D. Vandepitte, et al. "Full-field strain measurements in textile deformability studies". *Compos Part A- Appl S*. Vol. 39, No. 8, pp. 1232-44, 2008.
- [28] F. Stig, S. Hallström. "A modeling framework for composites containing 3D reinforcement". *Compos Struct*. Vol.94, No. 9, pp. 2895-901, 2012.
- [29] V. Chiaruttini, F. Feyel, J. L. Chaboche. "A robust meshing algorithm for complex 3D crack growth simulations". *IV European Conference on Computational Mechanics*, Paris, 2010.
- [30] G. Hivet, P. Boisse. Consistent 3D geometrical model of fabric elementary cell. Application to a meshing preprocessor for 3D finite element analysis. *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design* 42(1):25-49, 2005.
- [31] F. Laurin, N. Carrere, J.-F. Maire. A multiscale progressive failure approach for composite laminates based on thermodynamical viscoelastic and damage models. *Compos Part A*, Vol 38, No 1, pp. 198-209, 2007.
- [32] J.-L. Chaboche, P.-M. Lesne, J.-F. Maire. Phenomenological damage mechanics of brittle materials with description of unilateral damage effects. *US-Europe Workshop on Fracture and Damage in Quasibrittle Structures*, Prague, Czeck Rep, pp. 75-84, 1994.
- [33] A. Doitrand, C. Fagiano, F -X.Irisarri, M. Hirsekorn. Comparison between voxel and consistent meso-scale models of woven composites. *Compos Part A*, No. 73, pp. 143-54, 2015.
- [34] E. Obert, F. Daghia, P. Ladeveze, L. Ballere. Micro and meso modeling of woven composites: Transverse cracking kinetics and homogenization. *Compos Struct*; No. 117, pp. 212-21, 2014.